

Why “Post-colonialism” for Colonized and “Renaissance” for Colonizers? ...

Why “Post-colonialism” for Colonized and “Renaissance” for Colonizers? A Comparative Analysis of Deconstruction and Postcolonialism

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Abstract

The research aims to analyze postcolonial texts from the perspective of deconstruction. It is a theory that aims to seek the differences and hidden motives of any text. Jacques Derrida has given the idea of “Deconstruction” to uncover the hidden realities of the texts. The theory of “Deconstruction” is applied in the context of postcolonialism to explain the fact of subservience even after decolonization. The study applies the qualitative method with Belsey approach of “Thematic Content Analysis”. The study is significant because it negates the hegemony of colonizers after decolonization and it describes the hidden tactics of the term: postcolonialism.

Keywords: Colonizer, Colonized, Colonialism Deconstruction, Post colonialism

Introduction:

Post-colonialism is a negative term that is imposed on the once colonized subjects by the colonizers after independence. The term is negative because still there is the suffix of colonialism to remind the colonized that they should not forget their cruel past and slavish condition and exploitations. There may be many reasons for the term because the physical and formal colonialism has been ended by the colonizers due to decolonization and they abandoned the colonized countries according to their own wishes but they gave the impression that they left the colonized countries after the wars or movements of emancipation. In the past we were colonized, subjugated and exploited by direct colonial rule and in the present era post-colonialism is here to subjugate and exploit our present as well

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as our future. The process of decolonization was not done due to the wars or movements of emancipation rather the colonizers had completed the time span which was planned by them in order to fulfill their long-term planning which was hidden agenda to colonize the people forever and ever even after the end of colonialism. The term post-colonialism is one of the tactics adopted by the colonizer and the politics and hidden agenda behind the term is to make the once colonized busy and engrossed in their traumas and shocks so they may not look ahead for their own progress and they may not be able to compete with colonizers. The ideology of post-colonialism is invented and promoted by the colonizers in a very systematic way because the colonized were exploited by colonizers and they have coined the terms for different types of exploitations and they have done the job very well because the exploiters know very well that how they had exploited. These terms and theories about colonialism are coined by colonizers and the diasporas who are the product of colonizers.

Literature Review:

“Deconstruction” (1971) is an approach that implies the theory of different interpretations as it says that a privileging concept can be deconstructed in several ways. The colonizers did not use any negative term for themselves as the era after the tyrannical dark ages were not named “post-dark ages” rather they used the term “renaissance” which means “rebirth”. They did this in order to uplift and heighten the morale of their future generations but in the case of colonized they have kept the dark past alive which pricks the future generation and keeps them in retrospection of the horrible and dark past. After the dark ages, not even a single theory was invented by the English about the dark ages or about their exploitation by the Romans and French. But after decolonization, they themselves not only have invented a lot of theories but also, they have encouraged the colonized who have invented new terms and theories about colonialism or they have written novels about their exploitations. The colonizers have awarded the colonized who wrote novels, invented terms and theories, with different prizes and they bestowed their citizenship to their countries. They do not award them because they feel guilty about what they have done in the past with the colonized rather they award them to continue to write the same type of writing and do not look beyond their past. They only reward the people who write about their colonial past or who write about their deteriorated present omitting the positive and beautiful aspects of their countries.

Theoretical Framework and Research Methodology:

Derrida’s theory of “deconstruction” is applied in the study that is meant to understand the relation between the text and the meaning. It is an approach against structuralism’s ideal and static ideas that the meanings are not stable, universal and ahistorical. Deconstruction implies the fact that a text has multiple layers of meaning Derrida is of the view, “One term may be privileged because it is considered the general, normal, central case, while the other is considered special, exceptional, peripheral or derivative” (Balkin. 2004. P. 2). The term postcolonialism is privileged because it is coined by the west that is considered normal and the views of the colonized are considered peripheral because of the underprivileged condition of the colonized. The qualitative method is used in the context of deconstruction of postcolonial concepts as “interpretation always involves extra-textual knowledge. some of it is derived from secondary sources.” (Belsey, 2013. P. 161).

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Research Questions:

The study addresses the following questions:

- Why the colonizers have used the term postcolonialism for the once colonized nations?
- What are the reasons behind the abhorrent nomenclature of postcolonialism?

Research Objectives:

There are two main research objectives:

- To describe the true nature of the term postcolonialism
- To highlight the hidden and repulsive reasons of the term postcolonialism

Analysis:

World and people have forgotten or are gradually forgetting the disastrous and colonial past of the English people because the colonizers of English have not even invented a single term or theory for the exploitation of the English. They have very cunningly applied the exploitation which is done to them with more refinement as they say that Roman and French openly came to them for plundering, looting and domination. They came to England, exploited them and left them without showing any further concern for them but the English have come to the East under the guise of torchbearers in order to civilize the uncivilized and secretly they have plundered the sources of the colonized. The Romans and French left many colonial legacies in England as Christianity and the English embraced the colonial legacies open-mindedly, positively and they not only learned the lesson of colonialism from them but also applied it with more skill than the Romans and French. On the other hand, they do not allow us to forget our colonial past and for this purpose, they intentionally and consciously promoted colonial theories, terms, novels and intellectuals who write things about colonial exploitations. While on the other hand, Shakespeare has adopted Roman and French models, themes and stories in his plays and his all plays are the mimics of Roman and French themes. The English do not feel any shame and identity crisis in following their colonizers but they have invented many theories, binary oppositions and invented different terms about our exploitation in order to show us that we are not worthy enough to accept their models and way of living if we do so then we would be mimic men, hybrids and we have to face ambivalent attitude of the colonizers.

The English are very cunning and farsighted as they had exploited the colonized with different tactics and creation of binary oppositions is one of them. They not only exploited the colonized in the past but they are also exploiting their present and they would exploit their future by creating the binary opposition of Colonialism/Post-colonialism. In the past they had imposed ideology of colonialism, in the present they have updated it by adding the prefix of “post” which would be updated in future by adding another “post” but the world of “Colonialism” will always there in order to remind the colonized that there is no escape for them from their bitter past. In post-colonialism they have created different theories for clear demarcation of once colonized and still colonized. They had used the binaries of Sophisticated/Savage, Modern/Ancient, and Civilized/Uncivilized etc and now they are using the binary of Colonialism/Post-colonialism. They have to get rid of their horrible colonial past but they do not allow us to get rid of our miserable colonial past they want us to be haunted by our past and for this purpose they have imposed post-colonialism on us.

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Globalization is the product of post-colonialism and it is also another strategy of west to dominate the colonized. Colonialism has ended with the so-called independence but the motto of globalization or global village is a passport for colonizers to enter the country according to their choice. I say that globalization benefits the western only because under the so-called globalization they can still interfere in the East, if the world has become a global village, then why the Eastern are not allowed in coming and going freely without any problem regarding visa, or airport interview and custom checking. In “Home Fire” Kamila Shamsi and in “Reluctant Fundamentalist” Mohsin Hamid narrated the whole detail of their thorough interrogation and inspection as she says, “The interrogation continued for nearly two hours. He wanted to know her thoughts on Shias, homosexuals, the Queen, democracy, *The Great British Bake Off*, the invasion of Iraq, Israel, suicide bombers, and dating websites. After that early slip regarding her Britishness, she settled into the manner that she’d practiced with Aneeka playing the role of the interrogating officer, Isma responding to her sister as though she were a customer of dubious political opinions whose business Isma didn’t want to lose by voicing strenuously opposing views, but to whom she didn’t see the need to lie either. (“When people talk about the enmity between Shias and Sunnis, it usually centers on some political imbalance of power, such as in Iraq or Syria—as a Brit, I don’t distinguish between one Muslim and another.” “Occupying other people’s territory generally causes more problems than it solves”—this served for both Iraq and Israel. “Killing civilians is sinful—that’s equally true whether the manner of killing is a suicide bombing or aerial bombardments or drone strikes.”) There were long intervals of silence between each answer and the next question as the man clicked keys on her laptop, examining her browser history. He knew that she was interested in the marital status of an actor from a popular TV series; that wearing a hijab didn’t stop her from buying expensive products to tame her frizzy hair; that she had searched for “how to make small talk with Americans” (Shamsi. 2017, p. 9). The quoted lines show the contempt and disrespect of West for East rather than the positive implication of globalization. The contents of her suit case are searched thoroughly, her the most personal and private information is checked as she says that browser history of her laptop and phone history are checked moreover her views about dating websites, homosexuality, her views about subtle and crucial issues on religion are discussed which should not be asked according to the rules of ethics, morality and hospitality. But the situation is reversed in the case of a western or European. He is not interrogated and inspected in such a way if he comes to East. In “A Small Place” Jamaica Kincaid has described the contrast in which Blacks are searched to the extent of annoyance and Whites are not as she says, “You disembark from your plane. You go through customs. Since you are a tourist, a North American or European—to be frank, white—and not an Antiguan black returning to Antigua from Europe or North America with cardboard boxes of much needed cheap clothes and food for relatives, you move through customs swiftly, you move through customs with ease. Your bags are not searched” (Kincaid. 1988, p. 1). So, I want to prove that like other theories of post-colonialism, globalization is invented by the colonizers to suppress and oppress the so-called emancipated colonized and globalization only facilitate the colonizers. Colonizers know it, accept it and preach this discriminated attitude openly, without any regret, by awarding Shamsi, Hamid and Kincaid prizes. These writers are the lucky ones who reach the stage of interview of custom at airport but there are millions of people who even cannot get

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the visa at first place, there is no one to give voice to those people. This is very much insulting and derogatory act by Shamsi, Hamid and Kincad to accept the prizes from the exploiters. Their acceptances of the prizes show that they wrote this type of humiliated literature that shows the insult of colonized on airports as if they were ordered to write it. The reason behind the scene is to put limitation on the colonized so they would not write their issues because the colonizers do not want to give them voice. They have given voice to limited people by becoming their patrons so they write about relatively minor issues and biased point of view in order to satisfy the exploited people. The exploitations which are showed by them is limited than the actual exploitation.

Post-colonialism recaptures the history but it only traces the colonial history in which it does not look beyond colonial past. The reason is that the colonizers do not want to show our generation pre-colonial history. Pre-colonial history is a golden past which is contrast of colonial past. Achebe and Mad Bear try to show the peaceful and harmonious co-existence of different tribes but colonizers do not approve the past by giving it voice and recognition when they still call it uncivilized past, savagery and wilderness in “Heart of Darkness” and “A Passage to India”. Apparently Forster and Conrad show the sympathy with the colonized but they do not sympathize for exploitation rather they feel sympathy for their backwardness as Conrad says, “We were wanderers on a prehistoric earth,We could have fancied ourselves the first of men taking possession of an accursed inheritance,The steamer toiled along slowly on the edge of a black and incomprehensible frenzy. The prehistoric man was cursing us, praying to us, welcoming us—who could tell? We were cut off from the comprehension of our surroundings....

wondering and secretly appalled, as sane men would be before an enthusiastic outbreak in a madhouse” (Conrad. 1902, p. 57,58). Conrad has used the negative words for pre-colonial and pre-historic land. The land is pre-historic because the history of pre-colonized ear is not written by the colonizers. The history of the colonized starts from colonization and the white authors do not allow any history except the one written by them which is a very cruel and grave offence that the natives are not allowed to write their history and their past or pre-colonial era seems to be non-exist by the colonizers. The colonized are robed of their history and they are also robed of right to write their history themselves. Post-colonialism is an ideology which keeps the colonized busy in lamenting their colonial past and they do not try to look beyond it, they look neither beyond their pre-colonial past nor beyond their present to their future.

The module of post-colonialism is not taught at the basic and primary levels as at school level etc because of the assumed fact that the young minds cannot understand the severe condition of the past and they would not be able to get knowledge of horrible past as a result they would not react because of their careless or playful attitude. They would try to justify by different ways about the end of colonialism as the young minds mostly are more liberal, positive and friendly and they are more fascinated by the ways of living of the west than the mature minds and learned scholars. But the actual reason is that very little slot of students turns towards literature and most of them go for sciences and try to go to west either for studies or for jobs that’s why it is harmful to teach them about the past thoroughly by explaining different terms and theories because they would develop negative and harmful tendency for West and they would try their level best to serve their own country. So, at higher levels the course of post-

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colonialism is taught to continue the process of colonialism in the minds of the people who have interest in literature by imposing derogatory theories and terms as it is a way to keep intellectuals colonized. The people who go for sciences they remain ignorant about the past and they cannot develop the ambition or passion to serve their country in true sense as they choose science or clerical jobs to earn money. The situation of the Pakistan would totally be changed if our young minds are taught post-colonialism at school level as a compulsory subject in order to boost positive and ambitious attitude to serve the country with loyalty and love not only for earning money. Almost every young student wants to go to west either for studies or earning or recreation and they have a lot of complains for Pakistan and when they grow up the negative attitude toward Pakistan also grows with them, the situation would be different if they are taught post-colonialism at the basic level so they may not develop a fetish for the west and negative attitude for Pakistan. They are the future of Pakistan and they would be the politicians, doctors, engineers, clerks etc of Pakistan who would learn from the past and does not make the mistake of relying on the west for their benefit and they would have believed in their strength and will power. The last and the least benefit would be the end of corruption on the part of politicians as they would be aware that they have no other refuge except Pakistan. They would have relations with the west based on equality and respect not as beggars and citizens of an underdeveloped or developing country.

Frantz Fanon has presented the theory of “Wretched of The Earth” which apparently shows sympathy for the colonized but in reality, it demoralizes the once colonized people and their future generations. The second reason for the theory is that Fanon shows that violence is necessary to get independence and he approves of the use of violence on the part of colonized but the implicit meaning of the theory is that the colonizers had used violence to subjugate the colonized and the colonized were not innocent as they also used violence to take revenge so now both colonizers and colonized are equal in use of violence and there is no need to create a fuss to show the exploitations of colonizers because of even exchange of violence on both sides. Joseph Conrad in “Heart of Darkness” shows the use of violence on both sides when he says that a white colonizer killed a black chief due to a dispute on a pair of black hens and the son of the chief killed the white colonizer in this way both are equal in the exploitation of each other as he says, “I was told the chief’s son.... jab with a spear at the white man— and of course it went quite easy between the shoulder-blades” (Conrad. 1902, p. 12). In the novel again the blame is not put on the white man as it is told about him that he was “the gentlest, quietest creature that ever walked on two legs” (Conrad. 1902, p. 12). It was the sun and the rough weather that made him lost his mind and sensibility. Mr. Kurtz is another example who is the victim of hot weather as he could not bear it and he becomes a tyrant and savages like black people. He becomes their chief of the tribe, he kills people and puts their heads on spikes, he presides over their unspeakable rituals and only weather is responsible for all the exploits. Mr. Kurtz becomes an evil person because he has been living among those evil black people for a long time as Conrad says: “He had taken a high seat amongst the devils” (Conrad. 1902, p. 80). He calls black people the devils and Kurtz have become one of them. So, the colonizers are of the view that the black are savages, evil and devils by nature, they have the ability to turn the good people, like Mr. Kurtz, into savages and devils. The only tool to suppress the savages is violence. In this way “Heart of Darkness” is not written to show sympathy for the colonized rather it shows and highlights the savagery of the colonized. The

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death of Mr. Kurtz justifies that all his exploits are pardonable and he dies like a person who suffered a lot at the hands of colonized as he died by saying horror, horror, it was black people who made him their chief, he was their hostage and Marlow was sent to redeem him from their custody and Marlow was attacked by the blacks and he lost one of the members of his crew. It also shows that the colonized people who live in hot and tropical areas are evil and negative because of the proximity of the sun and they are helpless and in this way the mercy is shown to colonized in a way that the colonized are always inferior to colonizers even after getting freedom and independence because of cruel and hot weather. So, we are given the title of post-colonial subjects who are not different from their ancestors as they are wild, short-tempered, savages due to the environment and the colonizers are gentle, sophisticated and reasonable due to their environment. By laying the whole blame on the environment the colonizers have cunningly proved themselves innocent because they did not consciously exploit the black people it was hot weather that made them do so.

“Heart of Darkness” is written in 1902 more than one century has passed but still the horrible past of colonialism haunts the future generations it is still taught to a new generation and it is fresh in the minds of the new generation as Conrad has described the colonized or the black are criminals by nature. Whenever the wrong things happen the black are criminals and responsible for the crime. In the novel, a black is punished without any investigation. He is responsible for the conflagration in the store that burns everything to ashes as the writer says: “A nigger was being beaten nearby. They said he had caused the fire in some way.” (Conrad. 1902, p. 36). So, the colonizers warn the colonized to be vigilant in the future. The beaten, accused and guilty person has become a symbol for all black people. Fanon presents the idea by saying, “The colonized subject is always presumed guilty.... But deep down the colonized subject knows no authority” (Fanon. 1961, p. xxxviii).

The colonizers did not consider the black colonized as a human being and still the black are exploited by the white men because of the theory of “Negritude” which is a constant source of reminder that they are still inferior as in Hollywood movies blacks do not get the role of hero or if in any movie they play the central role, it would be the role of comedian as in “Wedding Ringer” and “Central Intelligence” they are heroes but in the characters of black comedian. The black are considered animals and beasts. Violence is the only tool to control these beasts and animals as Conrad uses the word of dog for the person who controls the boiler on the steam boat, “to look at him was as edifying as seeing a dog in a parody of breeches and a feather hat, walking on his hind-legs.” (Conrad,1902, p. 59). To support the claim the actual words of Fanon are explicit as he says, “when the colonist speaks of the colonized he uses zoological terms” (Fanon. 1961, p. 7).

Orientalism is another tool by using it the colonizer has put the whole blame of colonialism and exploitation on few western orientalist. The excuse of the colonizer is that it was the orientalist who did not represent the orient honestly and due to misrepresentation, they colonized the east in order to civilize them. Edward said in his book “Orientalism” shows that before launching colonialism on a particular area the literary people went to those areas for study and their study was biased and it is based on subjectivity as he says,

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Thus a very large mass of writers, among whom are poets, novelists, philosophers....have accepted the basic distinction between East and West as the starting point for elaborate theories, epics, novels, social descriptions, and political accounts concerning the Orient" (Said. 2003, p. 2).

Said has written "Orientalism" in order to pacify the colonized by blaming a few orientalists so that the colonized would not blame the colonizers by writing about them. It is a defense strategy of colonizers to show that they colonized the East mistakenly due to some misunderstanding on the part of the few orientalists who gave them wrong information about them as Said has introduced the term of "Strategic Location" of the author in the text. As Said says, "*strategic location*, which is a way of describing the author's position in a text with regard to the Oriental material he writes about" (Said. 2003, p. 20). So, the term blames the writer as he is responsible for the whole process of colonialism because the British citizens as Adela and Mrs. Moore represent the British people generally, innocent and good people who want friendship with colonized as Mrs. Moore has developed good relationships with Dr. Aziz. Mrs. Moore's kind behavior suggests that she is a newcomer in India as Dr. Aziz says: "I think you are newly arrived in India." Mrs. Moore invites Dr. Aziz to join her in the club. Dr. Aziz replies: "Indians are not allowed into the Chandrapore Club even as guests." The distance between the colonized and the colonizer is part of the plan of colonization. The colonizers want the wealth of the Orient. They do not want to establish a relationship based on equity. Hamidullah declares at the beginning of the novel that in England it is easy to be a friend of an Englishman than in India. Dr. Aziz, Mr. Fielding, Mrs. Moore and Adela Quested are kind-hearted people who want friendly relations based on equality but it is not possible because of colonialism. At the end of the novel, Dr. Aziz concludes that Fielding and Dr. Aziz will be friends in the future. Fielding asks the reason why they cannot befriend in present, Dr. Aziz replies that the relation between the colonizer and the colonized is the relation of power, domination and oppression which is not suitable for friendship. Dr. Aziz's actual words prove his stance, "No, not yet, and the sky said, No, not there." Postcolonial texts say that but there are very few bad-natured colonizers who create hindrance between the friendly relations of colonizers and colonized as Mrs. McBryde says: "You are superior to them, anyway. Don't forget you are superior to anyone in India except one or two of the ranies" (Forster. 1924, p. 40). So, postcolonial literature is the politics of the west in which the colonizers put blame on the few colonizers like Mrs. McBryde and redeem themselves from all types of horrible exploitations and brutality by criticizing their own few cruel people. They show the whole world that they are generous, honest, civilized, and upright because they have written books and novels on the bad and cruel behavior of their own people. Said has introduced the term "Strategic Formation". The term shows the relation between texts for analysis. All the post-colonial novels, which try to show the true nature of colonialism, possess the same features as violence, binaries, biased notions about Orientals and the exploitation of the black by the white:

"*strategic formation*, which is a way of analyzing the relationship between texts and the way in which groups of texts, types of texts, even textual genres, acquire mass, density, and

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referential power among themselves and thereafter in the culture at large." (Said. 2003, p. 20)

The term shows the artificiality and fake nature of postcolonial texts because almost all the text possesses the same characteristics without any originality and honesty. The same structure of the novels is that the author describes the context in the novel and there are always two parties in post-colonial text. These two parties are made according to the conflict. In the novels, the conflict is the fabricated reality of Orientals. The first party is biased and the other party tries to dismantle the so-called reality. So, the author is in the favor of the second party as Marlow, Fielding, Adela, Mrs. Moore and Mr. Frazer are the mouthpieces of authors in the novels. The novels which are written by colonizers, in which they show the exploitations of colonized, are the confession of colonizers but the deep structure of the novels the hidden agenda is to purge the colonizers from their sins and exploitations. They want to show the world that what has done is the fault of orientalists who misguided them and now they want a friendly and equal relationship with the colonized as in "A Passage to India" the dialogue between Dr. Aziz and Mr. Fielding shows the repentance of colonizers and obstinate nature of the colonized. The colonizer wants to be a friend of the colonized but the colonized is not willing as at the end of the novel Dr. Aziz concludes that Fielding and Dr. Aziz will be friends in the future. Fielding asks the reason why they cannot be a friend in present, Dr. Aziz replies that the relation between the colonizer and the colonized is the relation of power, domination and oppression which is not suitable for friendship. Dr. Aziz's actual words prove his stance, "No, not yet, and the sky said, No, not there" (Forster. 1924, p. 825) So, the whole blame is put on the colonized that they do not want a friendly relationship with the colonizers. The second example is the dialogue between Mrs. Moore and Mr. Ronny as he says that the Indians like and respect the people who rule over them like gods as the conversation between Mrs. Moore and her son shows the fault of the colonized and the necessity to subjugate them by the colonizers:

"We're not out here for the purpose of behaving pleasantly!"

"India isn't a drawing room." "India likes gods."

"And Englishmen like posing as gods" (Forster. 1924, p. 48).

So, the white writers do not show sympathy for the colonized rather they justify the ways of colonizers to the future generation of the colonized that it was the fault of colonized and it is not the fault of the colonizers which leads towards the process of colonialism.

The idea of mimicking man is presented by Bhaba and Said which is very much derogatory and insulting. The colonizers allow the colonized to adopt their style but they do not accept them and they do not approve of the humans like them. In the colonial era the colonized needed the mimicking hybrids to play the role of bridge between the colonized and the colonizers, they are the product of colonizers as a necessary evil but they are labeled as "mimic man" the shadow and negative copy of dignified colonizers. Colonizers have an ambivalent attitude towards their illegitimate copies of hybrids as they create them to use them but they do not like them and they are the type of people who are dangling between two extremes and lack of belonging and rootlessness has made them monsters and it has spoiled them also. After the independence, the psychologically disturbed and spoiled mimic men take

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the positions of colonizers and they take orders from their colonial masters which have continued the process of colonialism in free and independent countries that's why the colonizers give the name of post-colonialism to the era after colonialism to show the continuation of colonialism as Fanon says, “He turns into a kind of mimic man who nods his assent to every word by the people, transformed by him into an arbiter of truth” (Fanon. 1961, p. 13). Kincaid narrates that the colonizers have raised and trained a number of colonized people in order to rule the colonized after their departure and decolonization as she says, “....it was when it was dominated by the bad-minded English and all the bad-minded things they brought with them? How did Antigua get to such a state The government is corrupt. They are thieves, they are big thief” (Kincaid. 1988, p. 23). In the colonial era, Antigua was in bad condition and it is still in bad condition because of the mimic men who are colonized trained by colonizers. The mystery and question are why colonizers allow the writers to write the bitter truths about them and the answer is that they are doing so to keep busy the colonized in their past as it would not allow them to learn from their past rather in this way, they would remember their past and humility and by doing so their present and future would be neglected.

The theory is immortal and it is passed from one generation to another generation as theories of Plato and Aristotle are still taught to the students. The theory of Fanon “Wretched of The Earth” would be taught to our future generations in order to tell the sufferings and struggles of our forefathers in this way the wounds of colonialism would be fresh and unforgettable. The dilemmas of the past would not allow the learned and scholar generation of once colonized subjects to look beyond their horrible past and they would not be able to invent new and modern theories or they would not excel in modern knowledge as 71 years of freedom have passed and the Masters, M. Phil. And Ph.D. scholars are still discussing and lamenting the after-effects of colonialism instead of looking forward to new horizons and explorations.

Conclusion:

So, to sum up, the whole discussion we may say that it is not an empire that writes back to the center in “Reluctant Fundamentalist”, “Home Fire”, “A Small Place” etc rather it is the center that makes the colonized writers write about their exploitations so that the minor issues should be discussed instead of the grave and serious problems. The novels which are written by colonizers show that the colonizers are ashamed of the cruel acts which are done by some psychologically upset people like Mr. Kurtz who lost their stability in hot weather. The theories and terms like “wretched of the Earth”, “Orientalism”, “Mimicry” etc are invented to show our past that in the past we were uncivilized and wretched but, in the present, we are hybrid and mimic men who lack identity and their own culture. The reason for adding “post” with “colonialism” is to haunt our present in order to affect our future.

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